

Thiazole Derivatives : N-Substituted Phthalimides

M. PATRA and B. DASH

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-751 004

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A series of N-substituted phthalimides containing thiazole, benzothiazole and naphthothiazole nuclei have been synthesised. All the compounds have been screened for their fungicidal activity. Some of them have also been tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic activities.

N-substituted phthalimides have been reported to exhibit antifungal¹⁻³, antibacterial²⁻⁵, antitumor⁶⁻⁸, anthelmintic⁹, local anesthetic¹⁰, diuretic¹¹, adrenolytic¹² and schistosomicidal¹³ properties. Compounds containing thiazole and benzothiazole nuclei are well known as biologically active compounds¹⁴⁻¹⁷. In view of the above findings, the present series of compounds have been synthesised to study their biological activities.

They have been prepared by condensing N-hydroxymethyl phthalimide with 2-amino-4-substituted thiazoles, 2-amino-4-substituted benzothiazoles, 2-amino-6-substituted benzothiazoles and 2-amino naphthothiazoles. The yield of the final products are in between 60-70%. Satisfactory I.R. data and analysis (S and N) have been obtained for all the compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are not corrected.

Substituted thiazoles, benzothiazoles and naphthothiazoles

4-Aryl-2-amino thiazoles were prepared by the condensation of substituted acetophenones with thiourea in presence of iodine¹⁷⁻²⁰.

2-Amino-4(2'-thienyl)thiazole was prepared from 2-acetylthiophene, thiourea and iodine²¹.

2-Amino benzothiazoles and 2-amino naphthothiazoles were prepared by the method reported by Bhargava and Baliga²².

N-(N-Phthalimido methyl)-4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole

N-Hydroxymethyl phthalimide (1.6 g) prepared according to known method²³ was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol (20 ml.). To it 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole (1.76 g) was added and refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was cooled sufficiently. The solid formed was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p.

220(d)°, yield - 60% (Found, S, 9.41; N, 12.32; C₁₈H₁₃N₃SO₂ requires, S, 9.55; N, 12.54%).

The melting points of other N-substituted phthalimides similarly prepared are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C
1.	H	225
2.	Thienyl	170(d)
3.	Phenyl	220(d)
4.	p-Tolyl	138
5.	p-Cl-Phenyl	210(d)
6.	p-Br-Phenyl	130
7.	p-Ethoxy-Phenyl	185(d)
8.	β-Naphthyl	187

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C
9.	Phenyl	183
10.	6-Methyl-Phenyl	215
11.	6-Methoxy-Phenyl	185
12.	4-Methyl-Phenyl	225
13.	4-Cl-Phenyl	197
14.	β-Naphthyl	125
15.	α-Naphthyl	177

Fungicidal test

For fungicidal assay, poisoned food technique was used²⁴. All the compounds were tested for toxicity towards *Drechslera nodulosa* fungus which

incites leaf-spot disease on ragi (*Elusine carcava*) a millet crop extensively cultivated in Orissa.

The results of the fungicidal tests indicate that presence of halogens, β -naphthyl, and methoxy group increases the fungicidal activity (Compound Nos. 5, 8, 11, 13 and 14). The percentage of germination of conidia is ~ 10 and ~ 25 at a concentration of 500 ppm and 250 ppm respectively for the above test drugs.

Antispasmodic and antihistaminic activities

Of the four compounds (Nos. 2, 3, 9 and 10) tested, the compound Nos. 9 and 10 at a concentration of 100/ μ g/ml completely blocked the effect of both acetylcholine chloride and histamine on the terminal ileum of guinea-pig. The return of response after washing was also slow in these cases.

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